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Partnership in agricultural extension

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Partnership has been recognized as a strategy for attaining effectiveness and efficiency in agricultural research and development. Research and evaluation studies on this theme, however, are not adequate (Carney 1998).

A study was conducted in Chitwan, Nepal, to assess the effectiveness of partnership between and among government (GO), nongovernment (NGO), and private (PO) organizations. Through informal discussion and peer ratings, the District Agriculture Development Office (DADO) was selected as the GO, the Rural Reconstruction Nepal (RRN) as the NGO, and four private entrepreneurs (Inter Nepal Agrovet, Beera Agrovet, Narayani Agrovet, and Kisan Seva Agrovet) dealing with agricultural inputs as POs. Identified partners, together with farmers, selected the research problem and technologies related to the crop variety that farmers preferred—rice, hybrid maize, and sunflower. The partners divided responsibilities and agreed to work together through a memorandum of understanding.

During the implementation phase, partners reviewed the performance of the past month and developed programs for the ensuing months. After the implementation of the project in seven villages for 21 mo, data obtained from a complete enumeration of 123 adopters and 17 extension workers were used to assess the effectiveness of three individual organizations (GO, NGO, and PO) and four partnership (GO+NGO, GO+PO, NGO+PO, and GO+NGO+PO) patterns.

The study showed that partnership was more effective than nonpartnership in terms of crop variety use by farmers. Mean adoption was 8.4% for partnership and 4.3% for individual organizations. Five reasons explained the differences in effectiveness of institutions. Institutions under partnership performed their given responsibilities at a higher rate through comple-

mentation, provision of more resources (manpower and materials), and more professional use of agents' time. Other factors that contributed to effectiveness were peer pressure and mutual benefits.

The study also showed additional differences in collaborative efforts. Among partnerships, GO+PO and GO+NGO were more effective than other forms of partnerships (Table 1). The reasons for this include mutual understanding of each other's responsibilities, closely located offices at research sites, more frequent participation in monthly joint meetings, and a positive attitude toward each other. Among these patterns, GO+NGO+PO had the lowest adoption rate. The reasons were higher transaction costs and lower participation level in activities by the NGO due to project phaseout and staff reduction. This resulted in fewer farmers being motivated. Consequently, demand for inputs is lower. The PO's participation was low because of low demand for inputs.

Partnership was found to be technology-specific. Technology was classified as either high-cost or low-cost. Hybrid seed and associated technology were considered as a high-cost technology, whereas use of open-pollinated variety and associated technology was a low-cost technology. Among the effective patterns, adoption of high-cost technologies took place under GO+PO partnership. With GO+NGO partnership, low-cost and locally available agricultural technologies were adopted (Table 2).

Similarly, partnerships were specific to farmer circumstances. Except for the GO+NGO pattern, mean farm size of adopters was larger than the mean farm size of nonadopters. Significant differences, however, were observed only with PO, GO+PO, and GO+NGO+PO patterns. Among the effective partnerships, GO+PO mostly reached large landholders, while the GO+NGO partnership preferred small farmers (Table 3).

Table 1. Effectiveness of seven institutional patterns.

Pattern	Adopter farmers (no.)	Households (no.)	Adoption (%)
GO	7	154	4.6
NGO	17	287	5.9
PO	5	209	2.4
GO+NGO	22	271	8.1
GO+PO	52	311	16.7
NGO+PO	14	198	7.1
GO+NGO+PO	6	326	1.8

Table 2. Adopter farmers and technology types, by pattern.

Pattern	Adopter farmers (no.)	Low-cost technology (%)	High-cost technology (%)
GO	7	100.0	0.0
NGO	17	100.0	0.0
PO	5	40.0	60.0
GO+NGO	22	90.9	9.1
GO+PO	52	11.5	88.5
NGO+PO	14	85.7	14.3
GO+NGO+PO	6	83.3	16.7

Table 3. Differences in farm size between adopter and nonadopter farmers, by pattern.

Pattern	Mean farm size (ha)			t value ^a
	Adopter	Nonadopter	Differences	
GO	1.17	0.69	0.48	0.1250
NGO	0.51	0.37	0.14	0.1852
PO	2.40	0.77	1.63	0.0087**
GO+NGO	0.89	1.04	- 0.15	0.6110
GO+PO	1.23	0.76	0.47	0.0470*
NGO+PO	1.08	0.58	0.50	0.0856
GO+NGO+PO	2.02	0.62	1.40	0.0497*

** = significant at 0.01 level, * = significant at 0.05 level.

This study showed that partnership is an effective strategy but is specific to circumstances. Results suggest that partnership should not be generalized to be equally effective in all situations. Therefore, efforts should be made to develop partnership according to the local context.

Reference

Carney D. 1998. Changing public and private roles in agricultural services. London: Overseas Development Institute.

NEWS

International Rice Symposium Honors Chandler at Cornell

Dr. Robert F. Chandler Jr., IRRI's founding director, who died in March 1999 at the age of 91, was honored in a major scientific gathering held at Cornell University in Ithaca, New York, on 15-17 June 2000.

The Symposium, *Rice Research and Production in the 21st Century*, recognized his lifetime contributions to agricultural science. More than 150 scientists involved in rice research attended the international symposium.

Dr. Chandler, considered by many as a visionary, was a scientist of conviction and wisdom. His impact on international agricultural research is still widely felt today, particularly in Asia and in rice research. According to Dr. Ronald Cantrell, current IRRI director general, "If it were not for visionaries such as Bob Chandler, there may have never been a CGIAR and the makeup and strength of the national agricultural research systems—or NARS—as we see today in Asia and other regions of the world would be quite different."

Dr. Chandler was at IRRI's helm until 1972. Dr. Chandler wrote *An Adventure in Applied Science: A History of the International Rice Research Institute*. Before the Rockefeller Foundation hired him to establish IRRI, he was a professor at Cornell University. He later served as Dean of Agriculture, then President, of the University of New Hampshire.

In 1972, Dr. Chandler became the founding director general of the Asian Vegetable Research and Development Center (AVRDC) based in Taiwan, China. He remained active in international agricultural research even after his retirement in 1975.

In addition to honoring Dr. Chandler, the symposium focused on rice genetics and production in the context of international agricultural research management. Among the speakers was Dr. Norman Borlaug, who received the 1970 Nobel Peace Prize for developing high-yielding wheat varieties that, along with the IRRI rice semidwarfs, triggered the Green Revolution.

Sessions focused on "Intensive Rice Production Systems: Implications and Opportunities" and "Developments in Genetics: Future Opportunities in Rice."

The symposium was sponsored by the Office for Research, the International Agriculture Program of the College of Agriculture and Life Sciences of Cornell University; and the Cornell International Institute for Food, Agriculture and Development. Financial assistance was provided by a grant from the Rockefeller Foundation.

A 2-day reunion of former and current IRRI scientists, scholars, and dependents followed the symposium.

Source: *IRRI hotline* and *Rice News* of PlanetRice.net (<http://www.planetrice.net>)

